

ECOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE PARASITOFAUNA OF FISH IN THE TURTKUL POND FARM.

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Introduction. Great attention is being paid to the development of the fishing industry in our country. In order to introduce modern technologies in the production of fish and fish products, to create a competitive environment in production and provision of services, reforming the industry is being carried out in stages.

To successfully solve the fish problem, it is important to restore fish stocks in reservoirs and ponds, and to organize the fight against fish diseases and parasites in specialized fish farms.

The origin of fish diseases is not a uniform phenomenon. Certain types of diseases occur due to adverse environmental conditions, natural and artificial pollution of ponds, and other factors.

To increase fish productivity, it's essential to consider the origin of parasitic diseases. Moreover, the development of fish is close to natural waters in terms of ecological indicators. In this regard, the study of the parasitic status of valuable white sturgeon, grass carp, and other fish has both practical and theoretical significance.

Applied methodological techniques. The ichthoparasitological study of fish was carried out using methods developed by V.A. Dogel (1933), his students A.P. Markevich (1951), I.E. Bikhovskaya-Pavlovskaya (1969,1984) and others.

Research results. A study of 48 carp of various ages (size 3.1-3.4 cm, weight 1.3-1.4 g, length 13.5-19.5 cm, weight 12.0-8.0 g, length 21.5-31.5 cm, weight 105-270 g) in the Turtkul pond farm system revealed that their total parasitic infestation was 37.5%, with a range of 1-12 parasites, and 11 types of parasites were identified.

Among them, 13 specimens from the Yonbosh-Yop canal with fresh water were examined, and the total damage to parasites was 23.1%, with a range of 1-2 specimens; 20 specimens from the 4.6-meter low-flow reservoirs were examined, and the damage to parasites was 60.0%, with a range of 1-12 specimens; 15 specimens from the collectors were examined, and the damage to parasites was 20.0%, with a range of 1-2 specimens.

A total of 11 parasite species have been identified in carp, including 1 species of whipworms, 1 species of infusoria, 1 species of sporeworms, 1 species of myxosporium, 4 species of infusoria, 2 species of monogeny, and 1 species of cestode. Among these parasites, *D. vastator* 65.0%, range 1-12 specimens, *E. carpelli* 50.0%, range 1-8 specimens, *J. multifiliis* 45.0%, range 1-9 specimens, and *B. opsarichthydis* 40.0%, range 1-5 specimens were detected in relatively high quantities in the pools of sections 3-6, both in terms of quality and quantity.

Parasites of carp in the Yonbosh-Yop canal and collectors were found to be slightly less affected by parasites in terms of quantity and quality than in the reservoirs of sections 4 and 6, depending on the ecological conditions (water flow, turbidity, salinity).

Conclusion.

The Turtkul pond farm is producing high yield of carp. However, in low-flow 4,6 part ponds, in favorable ecological conditions for parasites, there is a risk of parasites multiplying, leading to the development of eimeriosis, ichthyoftriosis, trichodinosis, dactylogyrosis,

botriocephalus, and other diseases. Therefore, we must strive to comply with the epizootic and sanitary regulations we have proposed.

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